

Crystallisation of six compounds with ALK2 complexed with FKBP12.

Crystal mounting

All crystals were grown and mounted at 4°C before being flash frozen in liquid nitrogen.

25% Ethylene glycol was used as a cryoprotectant, mixed with mother liquor from the well and added to the drop before mounting.

The following crystals were mounted:

Compound	Crystal Plate ID	Well ID	Pin ID	Well Condition
PK012002a	CI070149	H4:d	E242	0.2M ammonium citrate -- 20% PEG3350
PK008982b	CI070145	F6:a	E240	0.2M ammonium sulfate -- 25% PEG3350 -- 0.1M bis-tris pH 5.5
PK012055a	CI070141	F5:a	C922	0.1M ammonium acetate -- 17%(w/v) PEG10000 -- 0.1M bis-tris pH 5.5
	CI070141	H2:c	E305	0.2M sodium/potassium tartrate -- 20% PEG3350
	CI070141	H7:a	C888	0.15M DL- malic acid -- 20% PEG3350
	CI070140	C7:a	C889	0.2M ammonium sulfate -- 30% PEG4000
	CI070140	F10:a	E530	12% PEG20000 -- 0.1M MES pH 6.5
PK012057a	CI070137	F9:a	E206	0.2M ammonium sulfate -- 25% PEG3350 -- 0.1M tris pH 8.5
	CI070137	H4:d	E251	0.2M ammonium citrate -- 20% PEG3350
	CI070137	H4:d	E214	0.2M ammonium citrate -- 20% PEG3350
	CI070136	A9:a	E308	30% PEG4000 -- 0.2M ammonium acetate -- 0.1M citrate pH 5.5
PK006099b	CI070133	D6:a	E528	25% PEG3350 -- 0.1M bis-tris pH 5.5
	CI070133	D6:a	C880	25% PEG3350 -- 0.1M bis-tris pH 5.5
PK010701a	CI070113	E9:c	E175	0.05M ammonium sulfate -- 30% pentaerythritol ethoxylate 15/4 -- 0.1M bis-tris pH 6.5
	CI070113	E9:d	E516	0.05M ammonium sulfate -- 30% pentaerythritol ethoxylate 15/4 -- 0.1M bis-tris pH 6.5
	CI070113	H10:c	E415	0.2M sodium citrate tribasic -- 20% PEG3350

At least one crystal for each compound was mounted.

Crystals were sent to the diamond light source for screening and data collection.

Data Collection:

Data collection was undertaken on beam I03 on 4th May 2018 by Joe Newman.

Two data sets were collected for crystals containing ALK2, FKBP12 and either PK010701 (1.6Å) or PK012055 (1.8Å). All other crystals showed either no diffraction or overlapping diffraction from overlapping crystals.

Data set details:

